

The Emergence of New Economic Words and Phrases in the Lexical System of the Modern Uzbek Language

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Abstract. *The development of economic terminology depends on social conditions, in this case, the transition to market relations. But at the same time, the development of vocabulary is determined by intralinguistic factors associated with the systemic nature of the language. Important changes are also taking place in the science of terms, as a result of which a new - cognitive - direction of terminology is being formed. The significance of the article lies in the fact that the composition in which it functions in the modern Uzbek language and the results of the study can be used in conducting integrated lessons, which will diversify the forms of education.*

Keywords: *entrepreneur, business, firm, merchant, auction, salesman, wholesale market, clothing, municipal, rethinking.*

The lexical fund of a language is an integral part of a unified language system. The fundamental changes that have taken place in the economy in the XX - beginning of the XXI century. They seriously affected the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. There was a rapid growth of the dictionary; after all, for each new concept, a new designation is needed, since great changes have taken place in the economy in the country. This could not but be reflected in the vocabulary. In addition, in the course of language evolution, the content-semantic potential inherent in the vocabulary itself is also used: changing the meanings of words, rethinking, building up new semantics, stylistic reassessment of words - all this, along with the birth of new words, significantly expands and enriches the vocabulary of the language, enhances its potential. The emergence of new words and phrases that reflect the phenomena and events of modern reality [1].

So, entire layers of vocabulary denoting economic relations under socialism are disappearing from use: collective farm, state farm, labor cooperation, socialist competition, superplanned. The words that were in the deep storehouses of the language, which were re-evaluated, are returning to active life: capitalism, entrepreneur, business, firm, merchant, auction, salesman - previously perceived in Soviet society with a minus sign, but now they have received a directly opposite assessment.

But in connection with the ideological and material differential society, the same words acquire different evaluative connotations for different groups of people. Deep processes in society are at work here - the social stratification of society according to the property principle. For new Uzbeks, these words (business, entrepreneur, etc.) sound unconditionally positive, it is an integral part of their image. For those who, as a result of new economic transformations, have suffered and simply become impoverished, these words are perceived sharply negatively. These are those segments of the population that have lost their social security. For example, marketers love privatization, but the people give it an assessment of the corresponding paraphrase - privatization, new thieves (14.08.2011). A new phraseology is being created: Uzbeks, shock therapy, shadow economy, money laundering, consumer basket, minimum wage. What is new in such clichés is precisely the

combination of words, and not the words as such. Each time has a certain set of words, which, due to the prevailing circumstances, become fashionable, widely and variedly used. These are a kind of "sign" words of the era. The mass media play an important role in their dissemination, creating a speech environment in which norm standards are set[2].

The word "collapse" (with the direct meaning "landslide") acquired a figurative meaning and began to be used to refer to economic phenomena: massive privatization, massive farming, massive fall of the ruble...

Lexical processes, as a rule, are accompanied by a transformation in the semantics of the word, its compatibility, as well as in its stylistic reorientation. Along with this, the newly created words are also known due to their wide use: lumps (commission tents), hitting (racket), flying away ("instantly" - the goods go flying away).

Semantic transformations in vocabulary, along with the nomination of new realities, contribute to the expansion and enrichment of the vocabulary. The acquisition of a new meaning by a word can lead to the birth of a new word, thereby strengthening linguistic homonymy. There are three main semantic processes: expansion of meaning, narrowing of meaning, and rethinking. Significant changes have taken place with many words that have long been known to the language. For example, the word "market" has clearly expanded its meaning or compatibility. We are accustomed to associate the concept of "market" with the realities of Soviet life - collective farms, state farms. Today there are: a wholesale market, clothing, municipal [3].

Expanded the scope of its use and the word "house". Until recently, we knew the formulas "house + clan. P." - House of shoes, House of weavers - i.e. specialized shops. Today, the names of trading and commercial firms have appeared: GUM Trading House, Insurance House, Biblio-Globus Trading House.

The economic processes of recent years have led to many language transformations. Most actively, new forms of social relations manifested themselves in various semantic changes.

The word "stagnation" as a term denoting "a time of slow development of the economy" also broke away from its primary use (stagnation in the blood, congestion in the lungs) and moved into the sphere of economic life.

The semantic processes in the vocabulary also include the process of depoliticization and deideologization of certain groups of words. There is a liberation of the semantics of words from the political and ideological connotations of the word: business, merchant, entrepreneur, private trader has lost the ideological increments of the negative plan. They were usually supplied earlier with a comment relating these concepts to the life of a capitalist society [4].

Now a neutral word reflecting modern reality, entrepreneur in the early editions of the Dictionary by S.I. Uzbekov, N.Y. Shvedova (in particular, in 2005) was defined as follows:

- 1) a capitalist who owns an enterprise;
- 2) enterprising person, businessman.

And the businessman, in turn, received a definition: a person who deftly conducts his business, not embarrassed in the means to achieve selfish goals. Here are extracts from the last building of the dictionary by S.I. Uzbekov, N.Y. Shvedova (2008.): entrepreneur:

- 1) the owner of an enterprise, firm, as well as a general figure in the economic, financial environment
- 2) enterprising and practical person.

But the meaning of the word businessman in a new formulation is a person who successfully (sometimes not embarrassed in the means) conducts business (exchange businessmen, dark businessmen). As you can see, the word "businessman", which retained a negative assessment, although somewhat softened, was replaced by a neutral one. Among the semantic processes in the lexicon, the question of changing meanings stands out; rethinking words.

Changes in the meaning of words occur in speech, which is based on the selection and combination of language units. The selection is determined by the paradigmatic relations of these linguistic units, their combination - by syntagmatic relations [6].

Differentiation of meanings within synonymic rows of words, caused by a certain pressure of some of the members of these rows on others, is evident in the case of borrowings, when a kind of "redistribution of meaning" occurs between synonymic units, caused by the emergence of new synonyms:

- devaluation – depreciation;
- offeror – offeror;
- guarantor – guarantor;
- investor – contributor;
- contract - contract - agreement.

Another process associated with verbal communication, with a combination of words, finds expression in the text. In stable contexts, a new meaning of a word is sometimes formed, which is then, as it were, isolated from the phrase and assigned to the word as such.

Thus, the constant or frequent use of a word in certain combinations, in certain speech contexts, can be reflected in its meaning:

- bank – mortgage;
- bank – dealer;
- bank – issuer;
- bank – guarantor;
- bank - an acceptor (a bank that has assumed the obligation to pay on the presented bill, account);
- business – trust;
- business center;
- business show;
- business club;

Here the word "business" takes on the features of an analytical adjective.

Modern linguistics considers metaphor as the main mental operation, as a way of knowing and evaluating the world. Man thinks in metaphors, expresses himself in metaphors [3].

The financial metaphor has long been used in Uzbek political language. The activation is connected with the strengthening of the role of commodity-money relations in the new social conditions.

The active use of financial metaphor in assessing political reality is one of the ways to manipulate public consciousness.

Consider the frame system of financial metaphor in modern political speech.

1. "Money (capital) and goods."

In economic terminology, a commodity is a product of labor produced for sale. In the modern political rhea, the authority of a politician, his voice in parliament, honor, conscience and other qualities in demand can be metaphorically presented as a commodity. "Political goods" sometimes serve as an export or import item: "To support the style of an unpromising candidate is a thoughtless squandering of political resources (V. Muminov); "Our soldiers should not die in the name of the export of reforms" (V. Karshiev) [5].

2. "Subjects of economic activity"

In economic theory, the subjects of economic activity are people or organizations engaged in commodity-money transactions.

For the successful implementation of the basic economic formula "Commodity - Money - Commodity", the company creates special structures: financial companies, joint-stock companies, stock exchanges, fairs, bazaars, shops that organize financial flows. It would seem that such institutions do not include political parties, parliaments, election commissions, but this restriction does not apply to the metaphorical depiction of modern growth. Political life: "Uzbek Parliament today is a big exchange where deputies earn money" (E. Samariddinova).

3. "Economic activity".

As you know, financial institutions are created in order to receive income from loans and investments in profitable projects. All this creates the basis for regular metaphorical transformations: "no dividends from this vigorous activity are received only by those who pay for the work of politicians, ordinary taxpayers" (M. Malikov). "Uzbekistan had troubles, but the political balance is positive for us: profits significantly exceed losses" (S. Karganov) [4].

The state organizes financial activities: it, if necessary, devalues and revalues the national currency. All these concepts are metaphorically used to denote political realities: "We are threatened by the devaluation of spiritual values, the results of which can be worse than any inflation" (N. Solikhov); "After the abolition of the federal districts, the gratitude of the governors is converted into the votes of the voters of these regions" (S. Madjidov).

The reviewed materials show that in recent years the financial metaphor has really turned into one of the brightest signs of Uzbek speech [7].

These processes are quite natural: the sources of metaphorical expansion and metaphorical attraction usually become understandable areas that are very relevant and arouse their increased interest.

It is significant that when using the financial metaphor, the authors, as a rule, do not resort to skills and other signs of warning about the unusual use of the word.

The use of economic terminology is updated in a wide range of communicative situations and genres of speech. The central zone of the functioning of economic vocabulary is a special speech in written and oral form. Moreover, economic terms are used by both economists and non-specialists, in whose active stock they fall. The mass addressee is typical for the media, as well as for some genres of urban speech - signs, advertisements, announcements. Memoir and fiction literature is a special zone of functioning of economic vocabulary.

The modern era has actualized many processes in the language. Language and society, as a user of the language, are inextricably linked, but at the same time they have their own life support laws [8].

So the appearance of something new in the life of society, just like the knowledge of new objects and phenomena, causes the need for nomination, which entails the formation of new words and expressions in the language or the formation of new meanings in pre-existing vocabulary units.

So the main ways of creating economic terms in the Uzbek language remained the same as they were before: word formation, word formation, the formation of compound names, borrowing. All these methods are actively used when naming new realities. In particular, the ever-expanding international economic relations, which contribute to an increase in the fund of the lexical system, become significant influencing the formation of lexical neologisms [9].

Although economic reforms do not lead to the creation of a fundamentally new language, they significantly increase the terminological fund, which in turn enriches the general literary vocabulary through terminology, where an important condition for viability is systemic qualities that contribute to the development of expedient and convenient means of expression.

Along with neologisms, a significant part of the words goes into the past, the other part is undergoing various rethinking, semantic and stylistic shifts.

The presented processes in modern vocabulary illustrate the active social factors in economic terminology - both in the field of semantics and in stylistic shifts, and in the activation of foreign borrowings. Modern vocabulary reflects the time of the formation of the new economy. Language dynamics is represented by new words:

- conversion,
- business,
- holding,
- marketing;
- returning old words to the asset:
- privatization,
- commerce;
- word update:
- profit, deposit, cash [10].

The departure of words into the passive of the language: super-planned, social competitions, all this gives a feeling of movement in the lexical composition of the language.

Consideration of the specifics in the word-formation processes of economic terms revealed a noticeable intensity of their flow. Despite the stability and traditional character of the main methods of word formation, the results of word formation processes in terms of the number of economic new formations obtained turned out to be significant. Particularly active is the production of abstract names, differentiated by type of activity (realtor, auditor, manager).

Words associated with the development of market relations (business, bank, entrepreneur), stratification of the population in material terms (state employees, payers, oligarchs) are active as a base for word production [11].

High productivity is revealed by word-building elements of a foreign language origin.

The use of economic terminology is updated in a wide range of communicative situations and genres of speech. The central zone of the functioning of economic vocabulary is a special speech in written and oral form. Moreover, economic terms are used by both economists and non-specialists, in whose active stock they fall. The mass addressee is typical for the media, as well as for some genres of urban speech - signs, advertisements, announcements. Memoir and fiction literature is a special zone of functioning of economic vocabulary.

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